

FROM PRESERVING NEWSPAPERS TO PRESERVING NEWS: AN EXPLORATION OF AI- ENHANCED PRESERVATION OF CHINESE HISTORICAL NEWSPAPERS

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Abstract – Historical newspapers comprehensively document various aspects of society, economic, cultural, educational, and daily life, serving as an indispensable medium for historical research and the understanding of societal transformation. This study proposes an AI-based framework for the recognition and structured processing of Chinese historical newspaper articles. The framework encompasses article region segmentation, identification of article titles and body text, and enhanced content representation. Experimental results demonstrate that annotation methods incorporating visual modifiers significantly improve model performance. The YOLOv10-based segmentation model accurately identifies article regions, while the detection model effectively distinguishes article titles and body text. By integrating with Optical Character Recognition (OCR) and large language models, the proposed framework enables automatic content structuring and summary generation, thereby substantially enhancing the readability and retrievability of historical newspapers. This work offers strong support for digital preservation, digital humanities research, and intelligent information retrieval.

Keywords – Chinese historical newspapers, digital preservation, article segmentation, article structure recognition

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I. INTRODUCTION

Historical newspapers, as important primary source materials, extensively document various aspects of society, economic, cultural, educational, and daily life and serve as indispensable medium for historical research and for understanding the dynamics of social transformation. These newspapers not only provide detailed first-hand information but also reflect the societal structures, public opinion trends, and everyday life of specific historical periods from unique contemporary perspectives. As both “witnesses” and “recorders” of their times, newspapers vividly reproduce the social landscape within particular spatiotemporal contexts. They function not only as supplementary materials for studying historical events but also as critical windows into the evolution of public consciousness and ideological currents.

However, over time, many historical newspapers have suffered from material fragility and inadequate preservation conditions, leading to progressive deterioration or even permanent loss. This puts invaluable historical memory and cultural information at risk of disappearance. Against this backdrop, the systematic digitization and

preservation of historical newspapers has become an urgent and essential task. Digitization not only facilitates digital preservation and efficient utilization of these documents but also provides a solid data foundation and technical support for future historical research, cultural dissemination, and public education.

The period from 1912 to 1949, marked by profound social upheaval and cultural transformation, constitutes a pivotal era in Chinese history. Historical newspapers from this period, as vital mediums of information dissemination, offer profound reflections of the contemporary social ecology, ideological trends, economic development, and the everyday lives of the populace. They serve as crucial documentary resources for studying modern Chinese history, the evolution of social structures, and processes of cultural transformation. Through in-depth exploration and systematic organization of these historical newspapers, scholars can gain access to invaluable primary materials that not only support academic research, but also facilitate the reconstruction of historical contexts, enrich historical narratives, and promote the contemporary expression of cultural memory.

II. BACKGROUND

In China, institutions responsible for preserving documentary heritage have widely adopted digitization and the development of thematic databases as primary strategies for conserving and utilizing historical newspapers. However, due to limitations in funding and other constraints, the majority of these databases provide only minimal metadata and offer relatively basic search and browsing functionalities. Typically, the metadata consists of coarse-grained descriptors such as newspaper titles, publication dates, and issuing institutions. In contrast, finer-grained content descriptors—such as article titles, section classifications, or thematic keywords—are often missing. As a result, retrieval is generally limited to broad parameters like publication title or date, lacking more advanced features such as article-level or full-text search. This creates significant challenges for users attempting to locate specific topics or historical events with precision. Only a few institutions, notably the National Library of China and the Shanghai Library, have implemented more detailed metadata that supports article-level

retrieval. However, these efforts primarily rely on manual annotation and cataloging of article boundaries and titles [1].

Internationally, the rapid development of digital humanities and computational linguistics has driven researchers to integrate semantic technologies, machine learning, and multimodal analysis to improve article extraction, semantic enrichment, and knowledge organization of historical newspapers. In recent years, semantic technologies have been increasingly adopted to enhance the machine-readability and interpretability of these materials. For instance, Erp et al. proposed building knowledge bases using language technologies and structured resources to address challenges such as language evolution and classification in historical documents [2]. Similarly, the HERO ontology project integrates an ontology-driven interface with algorithmic optimization and crowdsourcing to facilitate semantic metadata annotation and significantly enhance archival management efficiency [3]. These initiatives illustrate the potential of semantic technologies to bridge the gap between modern information retrieval systems and the content of historical newspapers.

To address the complex structural layouts characteristic of newspapers, researchers have developed various approaches that combine computer vision with text analysis. The Europeana Newspapers project, for example, utilized a pipeline incorporating OCR, OLR, and NER technologies to process over ten million newspaper pages, enabling both text- and entity-level search functionalities [4]. For more refined logical structure extraction, the *impresso* project leveraged a combination of visual-textual features and topic modeling to construct semantic indexes [5], while the *PlaIR* system employed multi-scale image analysis and conditional random field (CRF) models to achieve accurate article-level segmentation [6]. Notably, the African project demonstrated the feasibility of applying these technologies in resource-limited settings, using layout and color feature analysis to extract article-level information and support the development of public services [7].

Considering the current limitations in the digital preservation and utilization of Chinese historical newspapers and the demonstrated success of applying semantic technologies, computer vision, and text analysis in international projects, this study

aims to explore the use of artificial intelligence techniques for article recognition and metadata enrichment of Chinese historical newspapers. The ultimate goal is to promote the digital preservation of Chinese historical newspapers and enhance their accessibility and usability for research and public engagement.

III. FEATURE ANALYSIS AND DATASET CONSTRUCTION

Between 1912 and 1949, Chinese texts were characterized by the coexistence of classical Chinese and vernacular Chinese, with traditional Chinese characters serving as the dominant script. The writing conventions and grammatical structures of this period differ markedly from those of contemporary Chinese. In historical newspapers from this era, the predominant reading orientation is vertical—from top to bottom and right to left—though certain sections adopt the more modern horizontal, left-to-right layout. Furthermore, compared to contemporary scientific publications, the layout of these historical newspapers is notably more complex, often featuring articles that span across multiple columns. Such typographic and structural characteristics present substantial challenges for the accurate representation of newspaper content and consequently hinder efficient information retrieval.

While OCR technologies facilitate the initial digitization and recognition of textual and graphical content, the evolution of linguistic expression and syntactic patterns over time continues to constrain both the accuracy and recall of keyword-based retrieval systems. Moreover, the limited spatial allocation of individual articles, along with frequent line breaks and cross-column layouts, often leads to text fragmentation and discontinuity. These structural disruptions further reduce the effectiveness of retrieval methods that rely solely on keyword matching.

This study focuses on the Peking University Daily, a newspaper archived in the Peking University Library and published between 1912 and 1949. The publication has been digitized as high-resolution image files. The newspaper is characterized by a compact layout and a flexible typesetting scheme, typically employing large fonts. Most of the textual content is enclosed within clearly defined page frame lines, with only a few elements—such as the masthead or editorial notices—appearing outside

these boundaries. Due to the bound nature of the physical volumes, content located near the inner margins of the page frame is frequently obscured or cropped, rendering it inaccessible for analysis. As such, these portions are excluded from the scope of this study.

The newspaper's title is generally displayed in a large font within the "newspaper name" region. Given the physical dimensions of the pages—approximately equivalent to A3 size—the layout often employs dividing lines to segment the page into multiple columns. Common configurations include four vertically arranged columns or two horizontally arranged columns, with further subdivisions possible within each region. Other observed formats include two or three vertical sections, depending on the issue.

The Peking University Daily encompasses a wide array of content types, primarily concerning campus affairs and events at Peking University during the publication period. These include, but are not limited to, notices, official announcements, records of institutional activities, regulations, and course schedules. From a structural perspective, the newspaper content generally adheres to a "section-article" hierarchy, wherein each section comprises multiple articles, and each article typically consists of a title followed by the main text. However, in some instances, the section heading directly precedes the body text, omitting an explicit article title.

Articles also display certain consistent visual features. Titles are often printed in larger or bolder fonts for emphasis. When titles are arranged vertically (top-to-bottom), they are frequently preceded by triangular or circular typographic markers. In contrast, horizontally arranged titles (left-to-right) tend to appear in enlarged font sizes and may be accompanied by decorative horizontal lines positioned beneath the title text.

IV. EXPERIMENTATION

Our objective is to develop AI models capable of segmenting complete article regions and identifying key structural components, such as article titles and main body text, within Chinese historical newspaper pages. To this end, we annotate a representative subset of newspaper content and fine-tune pre-trained models to construct two specialized systems: an article region segmentation model and a model for detecting article titles and body text. Additionally,

we intend to leverage large language models (LLMs) to facilitate semantic enrichment of the extracted article content.

A. Feature Recognition

To enhance model accuracy in identifying target elements, we initially investigated whether the visual characteristics of newspaper layouts could contribute meaningfully to prediction performance. To examine this, we designed a comparative experiment.

A single bound volume of digitized newspaper images, comprising 144 pages, was randomly selected as the test dataset. Within this dataset, three categories of page elements were annotated using bounding boxes: sections, article titles, and article body text. We proposed two annotation strategies to explore the impact of visual cues on model performance:

Annotation Strategy 1: Annotate only the textual content, categorized by semantic type, while excluding visual embellishments or modifiers.

Annotation Strategy 2: Annotate both the textual content and its associated visual modifiers.

Illustrative examples of these strategies are provided in Figure 4.1, where Figure 4.1(a) corresponds to Strategy 1 and Figure 4.1(b) to Strategy 2.

Figure 4.1 Examples of two Annotation Strategy

To minimize annotation-induced variation, particularly for body text, a consistent annotation protocol was adopted. Initially, all page elements were annotated according to Strategy 1 to ensure semantic consistency. Subsequently, the annotations for titles and section headings were modified to incorporate their visual modifiers—if present—while maintaining the body text annotations unchanged. This process yielded two datasets: Dataset 1, containing annotations limited

to text, and Dataset 2, where annotations for titles and sections include both text and visual modifiers.

Following the methodology described in the DocLayNet study [8], we conducted experiments using three deep learning models: Mask R-CNN (MRCNN), Faster R-CNN (FRCNN), and YOLOv5. Model performance was evaluated using the mean Average Precision (mAP) across IoU thresholds ranging from 0.5 to 0.95 (mAP@0.5–0.95), which serves as the primary evaluation metric. All models were initialized with pre-trained weights from the COCO 2017 dataset[9] and subsequently fine-tuned on the constructed datasets. Experiments were conducted on a machine running Ubuntu 22.04.5 LTS, equipped with an NVIDIA GeForce RTX 3090 GPU.

The training configurations were as follows: MRCNN and FRCNN were implemented using the Detectron2 framework, with ResNet-50 as the backbone and an integrated Feature Pyramid Network (FPN). A standard 3× training schedule with default hyperparameters was used, with a learning rate of 0.001, a batch size of 4, and a maximum of 2000 iterations. YOLOv5 experiments employed the official YOLOv5x6 implementation by Ultralytics, with an input resolution of 640×640, a learning rate of 0.001, a batch size of 4, and 150 training epochs. An early stopping patience of 15 was applied to mitigate overfitting. A summary of the experimental results is provided in Table 4.1.

Table 4.1 Comparative Experimental Results of MRCNN, FRCNN, and YOLOv5

Model	Dataset	mAP	Section	Title	Text
			AP	AP	AP
FRCNN	Dataset1	0.743	0.875	0.657	0.695
FRCNN	Dataset2	0.751	0.881	0.614	0.759
MRCNN	Dataset1	0.732	0.860	0.673	0.662
MRCNN	Dataset2	0.74	0.893	0.561	0.759
YOLOv5	Dataset1	0.673	0.733	0.606	0.681
YOLOv5	Dataset2	0.757	0.867	0.639	0.764

The results demonstrate that models trained on Dataset 2 consistently outperformed those trained on Dataset 1 across all evaluation metrics. Notably, the YOLOv5 model trained on Dataset 2 achieved the highest overall scores, indicating the substantial benefit of incorporating visual features in the annotation process. These findings underscore the

importance of leveraging layout-specific visual characteristics to enhance the performance of AI models in structural element recognition within historical newspapers. Based on this conclusion, subsequent annotations and model development will fully integrate such visual features to maximize recognition accuracy and robustness.

B. Article Region Segmentation

In order to accurately identify and delineate complete article regions within newspaper pages, we employed polygonal annotation to label article areas. Given the irregular and non-rectilinear shapes of article boundaries, effective model training necessitates a sufficiently large and diverse dataset. To this end, we annotated four bound volumes of newspapers, comprising a total of 498 pages. These were subsequently divided into training and validation subsets at a 9:1 ratio, with 449 pages allocated for training and 49 for validation.

Building upon the favorable performance of the YOLO model family in preliminary validation experiments, we selected the YOLOv10[10] architecture as the foundational model for this task. Specifically, we employed the segmentation variant of YOLOv10 to investigate its efficacy in newspaper article region segmentation. As YOLOv10 currently lacks pre-trained weights for segmentation tasks, we initialized the model using the segmentation weights from YOLOv8 (i.e., yolov8x-seg.pt) and fine-tuned it on our annotated dataset for 100 epochs.

Upon evaluation, the fine-tuned model achieved a mAP of 0.885, and a precision score of 0.944 on the validation set. To facilitate a clearer understanding of the model's segmentation performance, we employed color-coded visualizations wherein each detected article region was assigned a distinct color, as illustrated in Figure 4.2. The visualization results demonstrate the model's capability to accurately delineate article boundaries, including those that span across multiple columns.

Figure 4.2 Visualization of Article Segmentation by AI Model

C. Article Headline and Body Text Recognition

Subsequently, we developed a model aimed at detecting and classifying newspaper article headlines and body text. Using the pre-trained detection weights of YOLOv10 (yolov8x.pt) as initialization parameters, we fine-tuned the model on Dataset 2, as described in Section A, over the course of 100 training epochs. The resulting model constitutes our final detection framework for distinguishing textual elements within newspaper pages.

Performance metrics, including the mAP@0.5-0.95 and classification accuracy on the validation set, are summarized in Table 4.2. These results indicate that the model is capable of accurately identifying and differentiating various components on the page, such as headlines and body text. To further illustrate the model's performance, Figure 4.3 presents a sample visualization in which all relevant textual elements are correctly detected and classified.

Table 4.2 Detection Model mAP and Precision

Class	mAP	Precision
Section	0.937	0.964
Title	0.69	1
Text	0.789	0.93
All	0.805	0.965

Figure 4.3 Visualization of AI Detection Model

D. AI Enhanced Metadata for Historical Newspapers

By integrating the two models outlined above, we are able to extract the complete spatial extent of each article on a newspaper page, along with the corresponding headline and body text regions. The application of an OCR engine to these segmented areas facilitates the extraction of both headline and body text content with high fidelity. Given that historical newspapers frequently utilize Classical Chinese—a linguistic form that presents considerable challenges for modern comprehension and information retrieval—we further employed the large language model Deepseek to generate summaries in Modern Chinese, thereby enhancing the accessibility of the content.

Consequently, the metadata associated with historical newspaper preservation can be significantly enriched. Whereas traditional metadata is typically limited to basic bibliographic descriptors—such as the newspaper title and publication date—the proposed framework enables the inclusion of article-level information, including OCR-derived headlines, full body text, and AI-generated summaries. Figure 4.4 offers a comparative illustration of newspaper metadata representation using the METS (Metadata Encoding and Transmission Standard) schema. Specifically, Figure 4.4(a) depicts a conventional metadata structure comprising only basic descriptive elements, whereas Figure 4.4(b) illustrates an enhanced metadata model that incorporates article titles, full textual content, and generated summaries, thereby providing a more comprehensive and

semantically rich representation of newspaper content.

Figure 4.4 Comparison of Newspaper Metadata Descriptions

V. CONCLUSION

This study centers on the automatic segmentation and structured recognition of article regions in Chinese historical newspapers. To this end, we designed and implemented a comprehensive recognition pipeline grounded in AI methodologies.

Through a comparative analysis of different annotation strategies, we validated the critical role of visual embellishment modifiers in enhancing model recognition accuracy. Experimental results indicate that models trained on datasets annotated with visual modifiers consistently achieve superior performance—measured in terms of overall mAP@0.5–0.95—compared to those trained on datasets lacking such visual modifiers. These findings underscore the value of effectively leveraging the visual and structural features inherent in newspaper layouts to improve model efficacy.

For the segmentation of article regions, we developed a polygon-based annotation dataset and trained a segmentation model based on the YOLOv10 architecture. The resulting model achieved a mAP of 0.885 on the validation set, demonstrating robust practical utility and adaptability—particularly in accurately identifying articles that span across multiple columns.

In the task of recognizing article headlines and body text, the model attained high accuracy across various layout elements, achieving an overall mAP of 0.805. Notably, it exhibited excellent performance in the recognition of section headers, with a mAP reaching 0.937.

Supported by this end-to-end framework, we successfully enabled the structured extraction of content from historical newspaper pages. In addition, we enriched the extracted metadata through the application of a large language model to generate descriptive summaries in Modern Chinese. This enhancement transforms traditional metadata—which is typically confined to fundamental bibliographic attributes such as title and publication date—into a multi-level structure encompassing article headlines, OCR-extracted full texts, and AI-generated summaries. Such enriched metadata provides a solid foundation for digital preservation, digital humanities research, and advanced information retrieval.

Our findings demonstrate the feasibility and effectiveness of applying artificial intelligence to enhance the descriptive metadata of historical newspapers. This approach not only improves content accessibility and retrievability but also amplifies the cultural and scholarly value of digitized historical newspaper archives.

Nonetheless, the current study remains at a preliminary stage. The dataset utilized is relatively limited in scale, and the model's capacity to generalize across diverse content types remains constrained. Future work will focus on expanding the dataset of Chinese historical newspapers, diversifying its content types, and improving the generalizability and robustness of the models. Moreover, we aim to explore the automatic recognition and semantic interpretation of more complex content types, such as tables and images. We also plan to pursue deeper integration with OCR engines and large language models to establish a fully automated pipeline for content segmentation, recognition, and metadata enrichment, thereby further extending the application of AI technologies in the preservation and utilization of historical newspapers.

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